

THEORY OF ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article describes the content of the implementation of environmental education, arming with knowledge related to environmental education in various age groups of preschool education organizations in different forms of introduction to nature: in classes, excursions, everyday life, observations, conversations, and at work.

Key words: Ecology, nature, environment, ecological culture, ecological awareness, ecological education, excursion, training.

It is known that the concept of continuous environmental education has been created in our Republic. According to this concept, children of preschool educational organizations are given simple elements of environmental education. In preschool educational organizations, children should be taught how to communicate with the environment, hot-cold, light-dark, night-day, rain-snow, kindness, birds, animals, and plants. It is necessary for them to know how to relate, to recognize the colors in nature.

The theory and practice of pedagogy includes – ecological education, – ecological education, – ecological awareness, – ecological activity, – ecological responsibility, – ecological belief, – ecological enlightenment, – ecological culture and a number of other related to ecology. Terms and related concepts are introduced. Ecological education is the main aspect of ecological enlightenment, and it is the transfer of existing social ecological experience from generation to generation in the processes of teaching and learning. Ecological knowledge, skills and competences are formed in a person through ecological education. Ecological education (in the narrow sense) implies formation of appropriate moral-ecological qualities in a developing person, and thus the characteristics of ecological behavior of a person are improved.

Ecological consciousness regulates the practical environmental activities and behavior of a person. Ecological activity means a set of actions carried out to ensure the protection of nature and the environment based on ecological

knowledge. By ecological responsibility, which is an integral part of the ecological outlook, we understand the responsible attitude of a person to the environment. Such an attitude is formed only as a result of understanding the consequences of the negative impact of humanity, in particular, some people, unknowingly and recklessly on nature, and the desire to eliminate such an impact. Ecological culture - exemplary moral-ecological behavior of an individual represents the state of being able to arouse pleasure in others. This term is used to define the level of attitude of individuals and society to the environment. Today, it is important to determine the content of all methodical and educational work carried out in preschool educational organizations, their organization, and the rules for choosing forms and methods. In this case, it is necessary for the preschool educational organization to introduce nature to different age groups in various forms: in activities, excursions, everyday life, observations, conversations, and work. allows to form taking into account the characteristics.

In the training sessions led by the teacher, elementary knowledge is formed in children in accordance with the requirements of the FIRST STEP program, basic cognitive processes and children's abilities are developed in a certain order. Children's personal knowledge accumulates during observation, play, and work in everyday life. The training allows them to identify and systematize. Teaching children in classes is carried out in different ways. It is important to choose the method according to the type of training and its main purpose. Children's basic knowledge is formed in some classes held in pre-school educational organizations. For this purpose, the educator uses observation, viewing pictures, reading works of art, telling stories, showing slides and movies. In other classes, knowledge is expanded and deepened. In addition to the mentioned methods, children's work in nature is also used in these activities. The main task of the third type of training is to generalize and systematize knowledge. That is why conversations, didactic games, summarizing observations are used.

Children apply the acquired knowledge in work and games. Classes are held twice a month for small and middle age groups, and once a week for older groups. Excursions are organized starting from the middle group. In addition, targeted walks are held in all groups. The effectiveness of the training depends on the level of training of the educator. The teacher should determine the topic and importance of the training, supplement the knowledge of natural science on the topic, and then develop training tasks based on the program. In doing so, the educator relies on the tasks of the First Step program, the child's ability level,

and the surrounding natural environment. When choosing the content of this training, it is necessary to determine its place in the work system (whether the process of forming initial knowledge takes place in the training, or whether they are enriched and put into a single system, whether knowledge application is practiced, and so on). Here, the teacher uses different methods depending on the purpose and content of the lesson. No matter what methods and methods the teacher chooses, he should use them in a complex, complementary way, this main goal is to improve the acceptance of the studied natural objects and phenomena by children and to serve the correct formation of concepts about nature. The educational tasks solved in the training are aimed at forming a positive, careful, caring, aesthetic relationship with nature.

It is important to prepare for the training and determine its structure correctly. The choice of the method depends on the nature of the educational tasks, the characteristics of the natural object, and the age of the children. For example, it is better to form knowledge about wild animals by showing slides and movies, and to get acquainted with animals and plants in nature by observing them directly. The chosen method should ensure the full implementation of the program task and active mental activity of children. Before training, the teacher prepares a number of visual aids, that is, animate and inanimate objects of nature (herbariums with seasons, calendars depicting natural scenes, stones, beneficial insects, plants and their parts, etc.). Because the visual tool gives children the opportunity to perceive the object being studied with several senses, that is, they can not only see the object, but also its properties (for example, try to scratch, hit with a hammer they test the fragility of things by bending, their elasticity by bending, flexibility, etc.). At the end of the session, the educator pedagogically evaluates the skills and abilities of the children, their attitude to the session, and their interests.

In short, comprehensive attention to the educational process of preschool children and their mental development ensures smooth and gradual acquisition of educational activities. This requires the educator to correctly choose various methods and tools during training.

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